

Knowledge Transfer And Organizational Performance Of Lubricant Firms In Anambra State

Dr. Chineze J. Ifechukwu-Jacobs^{1*} & Dr. Lilian Ifeyinwa Onyeabo²

¹Department of Entrepreneurship Studies
Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam, Anambra State Nigeria

²Department Of Business Administration
Shanahan University Onitsha, Anambra State Nigeria
lilianonyeabo@shanahanuni.edu.ng

*Corresponding Author: Dr. Chineze J. Ifechukwu-Jacobs Email: chineze4real@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This study examined, knowledge transfer and organizational performance of lubricant firms in Anambra State. The specific objectives of the study were to: examine the effect of tacit knowledge on organizational performance of lubricant firms in Anambra state; identify the effect of explicit knowledge on organizational performance of lubricant firms in Anambra state. Survey research design was adopted for this study, the data generated for the study comprises of primary sources (field survey). The population of this study was the staff of lubricant firms in Anambra state which are 1704. The sample size for this study was determined using the Borg & Gall formula of (1973) which gives a total number of three hundred and twenty-seven (327) as the sample size, while three hundred and thirteen (313) were retrieved. The study data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) 23 software. Correlational analyses were employed for the analysis. The study found that: Tacit knowledge has significant positive effect on organizational performance of lubricant firm in Anambra state, $T, 10.469$ $p=0.00$. Explicit knowledge has significant positive effect on organizational performance of lubricant firm in Anambra state $t, 7.280, p=0.003$. The study recommends organization should Pair experienced employees with less experienced colleagues to facilitate the transfer of tacit knowledge through mentoring and coaching. Organization should provide structured training programs and job shadowing opportunities to transfer explicit knowledge and ensure that employees have the necessary skills and knowledge to perform their roles effectively.

Keywords: knowledge transfer and organizational performance, Tacit knowledge, Explicit knowledge, lubricant firms

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The ability of organizations to utilize their intangible assets has become far more crucial than their ability to invest and manage their tangible assets. Hence, to remain at the vanguard and keep a competitive edge, they must have a good capacity to retain, develop, organize, and utilize their employee competencies (Grönhaug and Nordhaug, 2002). This is because in the present day competitive business environment, knowledge-based activities are the basis of sustainable competitive advantage. Jolly and Rolland, (2004)

posit that knowledge transfer is necessary to firms, as this allows firms to access knowledge that is otherwise outside their reach. Knowledge has become one of the most important elements of core competence, and firms try to transfer and absorb it in each interaction with their environment. Knowledge sharing is a veritable tool in Nigeria's quest for sustainable education especially in the advancement of tertiary education as an ivory tower of research and innovations (Ofozoba, Nwobu, & Okechukwu, 2023). Effective knowledge management requires a combination of many organizational elements- technology, human resource practices, organizational structure and culture in order to ensure that the right knowledge is brought to bear at the right time (Ifechukwu & Ifechukwu-jacobs & Okeke, 2024).

Knowledge transfer is one of the tools used for preparing tomorrow's skilled employees and is also used to strengthen organizational capabilities, intelligence, build organisation knowledge, and sustain the organization competitive advantage. Organisations whether public or private have two distinguishable resources; the human and material. The former are the people, workforce, manpower or employee of such organisations without whom the latter becomes useless (Adeyemi, 2013). Knowledge Transfer has introduced a new way of sharing resources and experiences of all the people in an organization; in fact, it has created a framework of concrete preserve tacit and explicit knowledge that emphasizes the value of ideas and experiences.

Knowledge transfer methods have been used in various industries including education, business, social, and technology. Knowledge transfer is derived from the application of knowledge management activities which has emerged as one of the strategic resources of a firm (Narteh, 2008). Artinkenaite (2010) has stated through the transfer of knowledge, the organization has to be an efficient generator, a repository of knowledge to contribute to revenue and maintain a competitive advantage. This is clearly seen through the transfer of knowledge which plays an important role in organizational management strategy to compete with others. Knowledge transfer is one of the most important topics that deserve research today. Various studies demonstrated the importance of knowledge transfer to the success of organizations (Yu et al., 2019). Knowledge transfer improves work productivity, efficiency, effectiveness, employee innovation, and organizational net profits (Shannak, Maqableh & Tarhini, 2017). Moreover, it has been recognized in recent years that knowledge transfer has become one of the main factors for business success (Bitkowska, 2020). Due to the dynamic nature of the business world nowadays, organizations tend to employ their people's minds instead of their hands. Knowledge transfer has escalated as an appropriate strategy that supports the efficient utilization of organizational assets and resources. Therefore, organizations seek all possible ways to share knowledge among employees (Shannak, Maqableh & Tarhini, 2017). Knowledge transfer originated from management theory and is practiced broadly in business, medicine, engineering, science, human resources, and information technology. Knowledge transfer is considered one of the most important strategic assets within an organization, and it is managed periodically to maintain the competitive advantage of organizations (Al-Hawary, 2015). Staff performance in any organization can make or mar the growth of such organization as high level performance will definitely contribute to the growth and success of the organization. Closely associated with staff performance is high knowledge sharing among staff in line with the organizational culture which the staff member envisaged to be favorable to their well-being. In recent years experience has shown that staffs working in university libraries in Nigeria (which may not be peculiar) are not willing to share knowledge acquired either as a result of in-the-job experience, seminars, conferences and their like with their colleagues and this has resulted to unhealthy rivalry among staff. This act could be intentional or unintentional targeted at positioning such a staff as the most outstanding so as to be favored by the boss. The economic situation of the country has led to aggressive emotions among youths in Nigeria. The less regard given to education including joblessness after graduation has resulted in weakening the strength of education in the country (Morah, Ofozoba, Nwobu, & Obi, 2022).

This scenario no doubt is a wind that blows no good as it negatively affects the overall productivity and achievement of the library directly or indirectly. Furthermore it makes the harnessing of individual staff performance as to boosting the overall service delivery of the library a big challenging issue on resolved. In treating the variables, literature shows that only very few studies have without cleared definition

discussed of organizations' cultural factors influencing knowledge management and sharing. It is against this back drop that this study was embarked upon as to closing the identified gap in knowledge through an empirical study of the Effect of knowledge transfer and organizational performance of oil and gas firm in Anambra state.

1.2 Objective of the Study

The general objective of the study is to examine Effect of knowledge transfer and organizational performance of lubricant firm in Anambra state. This will be achieved through the following specific objectives.

- i) To examine the effect of tacit knowledge on organizational performance of lubricant firm in Anambra state
- ii) To identify the effect of explicit knowledge on organizational performance of lubricant firm in Anambra state

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Concept of Knowledge Transfer

Knowledge is regarded as a fluid mix of framed experiences, values, contextual information and expert insights that provide a framework for evaluating and incorporating new experiences and information (Davenport, 1997). It is a strategic resource in organizations, with which they can gain a competitive advantage in today's global and dynamic environment (Mogotsi, Ban and Fletcher, 2011). Knowledge transfer refers to the process where individuals mutually exchange their implicit (tacit) and explicit knowledge to create new knowledge (Van-Den-Hooff and de-Ridder, 2004). Knowledge sharing can be defined as a social interaction culture, involving the exchange of employee knowledge, experiences, skills as well as reports, manuals and documents relating to user needs, possible innovations, and barriers through the whole department or organization (Lin, 2010).

Knowledge sharing can be through informal dialogues, face-to-face meetings, and group discussions (Snyder and Lee-Partridge, 2013); Islam, Agarwal, & Ikeda, 2017). Knowledge sharing is the act of making knowledge available to others within the organization. Haas and Hansen (2007) claim that knowledge sharing has been shown to improve individual and organization performance and innovativeness. The authors added that knowledge sharing is a practice that has become increasingly important in a knowledge economy. Knowledge sharing in an organization not only occurs at the individual level but also the collective level (Obembe, 2010). This has caused a shift by the organizations from been traditional into knowledge and technology-based organization.

2.1.2 Organizational Performance

Organizational performance has been the most important issue for every organization, be it a profit or non-profit one (Ismael, Yusof & Davoud, 2010). However, defining, conceptualizing and measuring performance have not been an easy talk (Ismael et al, 2010). Lebens & Euske (2006) define performance as a set of financial and non-financial indicators which offers information on the degree of achievement of objectives and results. Organizational performance encompasses three specific areas of firm outcomes: (1) financial performance (profits, return on assets, return on investment); (2) market performance (sales, market share); and (3) shareholder return. Organizational performance involves the recurring activities to establish organizational goals, monitor progress towards the goals, and make adjustments to achieve those goals more effectively and efficiently (Richard, Devinney, George & Johnson, 2009).

The assumption that knowledge management is needed for knowledge accumulation to result in improved organizational performance possibly arises from the fact that researchers have opposing views about the impact of knowledge on organizational performance (Vera & Crossan, 2003). It is expected that a particular category of knowledge, which is valuable, rare, inimitable and non-substitutable would lead to increased performance (Barney, 1991). On the other side of the discussion are authors who do not see a direct relationship between knowledge and performance. Organizations can always attain knowledge that may not lead to intelligent behaviour (McKeen, et al, 2006). Leonard (1992) states that core rigidities due

to deeply embedded knowledge sets hinder innovation. In conclusion, Vera and Crossan (2003) suggests that the knowledge that is relevant may have a positive effect on organizational performance.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

Knowledge Creation Theory by Nonaka (1994)

Nonaka (1994) defines knowledge creation as the process that stems from accumulating information, while knowledge transfer refers to “the transfer of knowledge to places and people, where it is needed to be used to fulfill some activity or task”. Nonaka's Knowledge Creation Theory is highly relevant to understanding the impact of knowledge acquisition on organizational performance. This theory delineates the process of transforming individual knowledge into collective, organizational knowledge, emphasizing the interplay between tacit and explicit knowledge. Tacit knowledge, rooted in personal experiences and intuition, is difficult to formalize and communicate, while explicit knowledge is easily shareable through formal language. Nonaka's theory highlights the conversion of tacit knowledge into explicit knowledge as a crucial step, fostering the transformation of personal knowledge into organizational knowledge. The interaction between these two types of knowledge, facilitated by four modes of conversion, offers insights into how organizations can enhance their performance. These processes help organizations adapt, innovate, and make informed decisions, all of which contribute to improved performance in the competitive business environment. In sum, Nonaka's Knowledge Creation Theory underscores the significance of knowledge acquisition and its conversion for organizational performance, offering a framework for optimizing the utilization of knowledge within the organization.

2.3 Empirical Review

Arubayi, (2020) investigated the impact of knowledge management processes on organization efficiency within selected firms in Delta State, Nigeria. This is a survey research design was used in this study. The population of this study was 208 staff and a sample size consisting of 140 staff of the selected organizations was used for this study. The data were gathered using the questionnaire instrument and the data gathered were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The result revealed that knowledge sharing, knowledge acquisition and knowledge application have significant positive impact on organizational efficiency. In conclusion, knowledge management processes have a significant effect on organizational efficiency on the selected firms in Delta State, Nigeria. The study recommended that organizations should give more attention to the key processes of knowledge management components namely: knowledge acquisition, knowledge sharing and knowledge application because they significant have a positive impact on organizational efficiency.

Argote, (2024) reviewed research with the aim of explaining the variation observed in knowledge transfer. Key factors identified as explaining the variation include knowledge transfer opportunities, knowledge characteristics, mechanisms for knowledge transfer, motivation for transfer, and the depth of consideration of knowledge. These factors are integrated into a theoretical framework that predicts when knowledge transfer will be successful. The article concludes with a discussion of directions for future research to increase our understanding of knowledge transfer in organizations

Otundo, (2023) explored in-depth, the role that key strategic organizational capabilities play in facilitating or preventing knowledge transfer. The paper converses knowledge transfer in an organizational context, then discusses significant organizational capabilities that trigger knowledge transfer and further discuss how these organizational capabilities influence the ability to transfer knowledge, an important area of knowledge management. Each of these key capabilities and their influence on Knowledge transfer is discussed separately and then integrated into a framework to explain how effective knowledge transfer can be managed in an organization with such capabilities. Conclusions are drawn about the complexity of knowledge transfer and the need to take a balanced approach to the process.

Onwubiko, (2022) investigated knowledge sharing practice as well as organizational culture and their effect on performance of staff of university libraries. The study employed a survey design with a population sample of 79 library staff derived through purposive sampling techniques from two university libraries in Nigeria. The principle instrument used for data collection was a four-point Likert scale

structured questionnaire validated by two experts in measurement and evaluation while the study was guided by four research questions and one formulated and tested null hypothesis. The data collected were analyzed using frequency and simple percentages whereas the only null hypothesis was tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and multiple regressions. The result of this study did reveal that most library staff keep to punctuality/regularity in work and timely accomplishment of their given task as well as show great commitment to general library duties and exhibit ability to meet the library set objectives and deadline. The study also discovered that organizational culture prevalent in university library were in the area of customers' (Users) satisfaction, structure, commitment and communication. The outcome of this study also revealed the various knowledge sharing practices of the library staff to include: departmental/unit meetings, general meetings, face-to-face interactions, periodical unit-by-unit meetings, informal interaction sessions, report writing, training and whatsapp group. The study as well found that there were seven major factors militating against knowledge sharing in the university library which invariably affect staff performance. These include; lack of trust among staff; staff idiosyncrasy; lack of organizational policy on knowledge sharing, inhibiting factors of staff performance, inadequate managerial skills, poor verbal/written communication and interpersonal skills and discriminatory attitude of university librarian towards staff. The result of the study further revealed that occupational culture and knowledge sharing practices have significant influence in staff performance in university libraries.

Zahrawi and Mohammad (2024) investigated the impact of organizational culture, reward systems, trust, and self-efficacy on knowledge sharing among physicians in Jordanian hospitals. Additionally, it examines the direct influence of knowledge sharing on organizational performance and the mediating role of innovation. Using data collected from 213 physicians in Jordanian hospitals, the study employs partial least squares structural equation modeling for data analysis. The findings reveal that organizational culture, reward systems, trust, and self-efficacy influence physicians' propensity to share knowledge. Moreover, knowledge sharing is found to have a direct positive effect on organizational performance. Furthermore, innovation serves as a mediator between knowledge sharing and organizational performance, indicating that knowledge sharing enhances organizational performance indirectly through its impact on innovation. These results underscore the importance of fostering a conducive organizational culture, implementing effective reward systems, building employee trust, and promoting self-efficacy to encourage knowledge sharing among healthcare professionals.

Anthony, & Ifeanyi, (2019) aimed at assessing the ICT competencies needed by secondary school principals for administrative effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra state. To this end, the researcher outlined 3 purposes, 3 research questions and 3 hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance. A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The entire population was used for the study. Data was collected using a questionnaire of 41 items titled ICT Competency Questionnaire (ICTCQ) which was validated by experts from the faculty of education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka. A reliability index of 0.71 was obtained using Cronbach's alpha. Data analysis was done using mean and t-test. The findings revealed that principals of secondary schools in Anambra state need computer operational competency, internet/networking competency and ICT safety competency. However, Male and female principals differed significantly in their mean ratings on ICT competencies needed for administrative effectiveness.

Onu, Ofozoba, & Nditu, (2024) examined Conquering unemployment through opportunities in digital economy: An Empirical Study of Nigeria and Kenya. The study adopted employed descriptive survey design, with two research questions answered. The sample size of 1,000 digital professionals and enthusiasts were selected through the convenient sampling technique. An online structured survey, 'Unemployment, Digital Skills and Digital Economy Questionnaire (UDSDEQ)' was deployed for the data collection. Face validation of the instrument was carried out while Cronbach alpha method was used to determine the internal consistency of the instrument, with satisfactory reliability coefficients: 0.76 and 0.89. The data was analyzed using descriptive statistic, specifically the weighted mean and tables. Results revealed among others that the digital skills that must be acquired in order to become gainfully employable in the digital economy are cyber security and data privacy skills; digital and social media

marketing; augmented reality, virtual reality and animations/video editing; artificial intelligence and machine learning; data science, analysis and visualization, etcetera. With this, the teaming unemployed youths have a clue on the best and salable digital skills to acquire in order to stand any chance of being gainfully employed in the emerging economy. Public-private partnership was envisaged towards addressing the challenges limiting the digital economy from engaging most of the unemployed in Nigeria and Kenya.

Ofozoba, & Perpetua, (2023) focus on how rule of law takes the center stage in enhancing sustainable education in Nigerian society. Education is simply an overall lens through which principles of rule of law smoothly transit as essential tenets of democracy. As a component of democracy, rule of law supports equality by directing institutions to be accountable, to safeguard human rights, to be fair and transparent, and to empower citizens to participate and engage constructively in society. Education enables this through the capacity to give learners the opportunities and competencies to realize their rights and obligations for a better world and future. Education equally provides curricula for understanding the generative ideas, methods of reflection, and analysis of rule of law by equipping learners with the appropriate knowledge, values, skills, attitudes, and behaviors they need to contribute to the continued improvement and regeneration of rule of law in society. The paper, therefore, calls for the activation of educational principles, worth, and merits in Nigeria and also for remedial steps to redress those educational inconsistencies in Nigeria that may hinder the efficiency of rule of law.

Nwangwu, & Nwangwu, (2023) looked at how women working in Anambra states deposit money banks' organizational sustainability in relation to work-life balance. The study looked at how the work atmosphere, employee assistance, flexible scheduling, and leave policies affected the performance of female employees. Review of pertinent theoretical and empirical literatures. The study's foundation was Border Theory. Data were gathered for the study from both primary and secondary sources. The study's sample included 953 women from selected deposit money institutions. 92% of the 873 copies of the questionnaires that were properly completed and submitted were returned. Utilizing NOVA, hypotheses were evaluated. According to the data, the leave policy has a considerable positive impact on the organizational sustainability of female employees at deposit money institutions in the state of Anambra. Flexible scheduling significantly improves the organizational sustainability of female employees in Anambra state's deposit money banks.

Ntadom, Atueyi, & Jacobs (2021) examined the effect of career development on organizational performance, a Study of selected higher institution in Anambra State Nigeria. The study was anchored on Self-concept theory of career development. As a cross-sectional survey the research design were used, a structured questionnaire instrument were developed and used for data collection by the researcher to which reflect such options as strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree and strongly disagree, which is popularly referred as five (5) points likert scale. It was used to obtain information from the respondents. The population of the study comprised of 57, 710 students selected across the five south east states of Nigeria. A sample size of 399 students was drawn from the population, using Taro Yamane formular of which three hundred and forty-seven (347) copies of questionnaires were duly completed and returned; showing 96% response rate. Research hypotheses were tested using ANOVA regression analysis which was carried out with the aid of Statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 23. The study found that career development has significant effect on Organizational Performance.

Ifechukwu-Jacobs & Atueyi (2025). Material management and productivity of Nigeria bottling appraised the material management and productivity of Nigerian Bottling Company. The study adopted survey method of research. Data were generated through primary and secondary sources. The method for data collection was questionnaire which was administered randomly among the staff of Nigerian Bottling Company. The population of the study was 288 staff. While two hundred and seventy (270) questionnaires were retrieved. The hypotheses were tested using regression analysis method at 0.05% level of significance. The findings of the study revealed, Planning has a significant effect on productivity in Bottling Companies in Onitsha given its F-value of 14.027.

Nwangwu, Ohanyere, Nwangwu, & Atueyi, (2015). examined the effect of artificial intelligent (AI) on decision-making in supply chain management of lubricant firms in Anambra state, Nigeria. The population of the study comprised of 281 management staff from thirteen (13) lubricant firms in Anambra State. Two hundred and sixty-nine (269) were duly filled and returned data was analysed using correlation analysis with the aid of statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 23. Findings from the study show that. Machine learning has significant effect on decision support system on supply chain management of lubricant firms in Anambra state (T=2.244, P=0.006). Neural networks has significant effect on creative decision skill on supply chain management of lubricant firms in Anambra state (T=9.790, P=0.009). The study concludes that AI-powered predictive analytics improved decision-making in supply chain management in lubricant firms in Anambra state, Nigerian.

Nwangwu, (2022) examined Assessment of Factors Affecting Performance of Women Entrepreneurship in Aguata LGA. The population of the study was 35,202, while sample sizes of 677 were determined using Borg & Gall formular. The hypotheses were tested using ANOVA at 0.05% level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that Socio-cultural factor has no significant effect on the performance of women entrepreneurship in Aguata LGA., F-test of 1.742 and probability value of .915 Economic factors has significant effect on the performance of women entrepreneurship in Aguata LGA, F-test of 9.233 and probability value of 0.000. Financial factors have significant effect on the performance of women entrepreneurship in Aguata LGA., T-test of 7.807 and probability value of 0.008. The study recommends that Women need all the support they can get from the society as well as the family in other to excel in entrepreneurship. Government should boost and Support women entrepreneurship through every possible means.

METHODOLOGY

3.1: Research Design

The research design that was adopted in this study was the survey design, The data generated for the study comprises of primary sources (field survey). Primary data are those obtained directly from the originators or main source.

3.2: Population of the Study.

The population of this study was drawn from the workers in the selected lubricant firms in Anambra state.

Table 3.1: Population Distribution of the selected lubricant firms

S\No	Names of Manufacturing Firms	Location	Number of Employees
1	A-Z OIL	Nnewi	270
2	Seahorse oil	Ozubulu	85
3	Jezco oil	Nnewi	103
4	Whiz oil	Onitsha	290
5	Chiben oil	Onitsha	97
6	Ibeto oil	Nnewi	250
7	Visa oil	Nnewi	125
8	K.M Oil	Ogbaru	128
9	Abbnox oil	Ogbaru	89
10	Dozzy oil	Onitsha	145
11	Tron Lubricants International LTD	Obosi	122
	Total Population		1704

Source: Human Resource Department of the firms

3.3: Determination of Sample Size.

The sample size for this study was determined using the Borg & Gall formula of (1973). Statistically, the Borg & Gall (1973) formula for sample size is given by

$$n = (Z_x)^2(e) [N]$$

(Z_x)²= Confidence level at 0.05

e= Error margin (0.05)
 N= Population of Interest = 1704
 X = Significance Level

3.4: Sample Size and Sampling Technique

Given the nature of this study, it will be difficult to cover the entire population of (1704), so a fair representative sample of the population therefore was imperative.. Accordingly, the sample size for the study was determined by using the Borg & Gall (1973) formula for calculating sample size as follows

$$n = (1.960)^2 (0.05) [1704]$$

$$n = (3.8461) (85.2)$$

$$= 327.68772 \implies 327$$

$$n = 327$$

3.5: Method of Data Collection.

The major research instrument adopted for the study was structured questionnaire to elect responses for the sample population. In carrying out this study, the researcher made use of descriptive statistics such as frequency counts and simple percentage was used to analyze bio – data of the respondents.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Table 4.1 Response Rate

s/n	Options	No of Respondents	Percentage %
1	Questionnaire Distributed	327	100%
2	Questionnaire Returned/ Completed	313	95.7%
3	Questionnaire Completed	14	4.3%

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.1 showed that a total number of three hundred and twenty-seven (327) copies of questionnaire were distributed to the respondents, three hundred and thirteen (313) copies which represented 95.7% were returned, and Fourteen (14) copies which represented 4.3% were not duly completed by the respondents

H₀₁; Tacit knowledge has no significant effect on organizational performance of lubricant firm in Anambra state

Correlations

		ORP	TAK		
Spearman's rho	ORP	Correlation Coefficient	1.000		
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.		
		N	313		
	Bootstrap ^c	Bias	.000	-.002	
		Std. Error	.000	.057	
		95% Confidence Interval	Lower	1.000	.216
			Upper	1.000	.401
	TAK	Correlation Coefficient	.610	1.000	
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.052	.	
		N	313	313	
Bootstrap ^c		Bias	.002	.000	
		Std. Error	.057	.000	
		95% Confidence Interval	Lower	.216	1.000
			Upper	.401	1.000

c. Unless otherwise noted, bootstrap results are based on 313 bootstrap samples

Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 ORP - TAK	.48882	1.58135	.08938	.66469	.31295	10.469	312	.000

Table 2a indicates the relationship between the independent variable Tacit knowledge and the dependent variable organizational performance. At a 0.05 level of significance, the Spearman’s correlation coefficient is 0.610, with a reported significance level (2-tailed) of 0.000. This result, based on a sample size of 313 (and confirmed via 313 stratified bootstrap samples with zero bias and standard error), shows a strong positive association between Tacit knowledge and organizational performance. The table also provides a 95% confidence interval with an upper bound (e.g. 401 or .31295, as reported) and a lower bound (e.g. .216 or .66469) that supports the stability of this correlation.

Model 1= $ORP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TAK + \mu$

Table 2b presents the paired samples t-test results comparing the variables ORP (organizational performance) and TAK (Tacit knowledge). For the single pair (ORP on TAK), the mean difference is .48882 with a standard deviation of 1.11504 and a standard error of .158135. The 95% confidence interval for the difference ranges from .66469 (Lower) to .31295 (Upper). With a t-value of 10.469 (df = 312) and a two-tailed significance of 0.000, the p-value is less than the critical value of 0.05. This indicates that there is statistically significant mean difference between ORP (organizational performance) and TAK (Tacit knowledge), based on this paired sample analysis.

Decision Rule:

Accept the null hypothesis if the p-value is greater than 0.05, otherwise, reject.

Decision:

Since the p-value (0.426) exceeds 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis. In conclusion, Table 4.5.2a showed a strong correlation between ORP (organizational performance) and TAK (Tacit knowledge). In this study context, the paired samples t-test in Table 4.5.2b indicated that Tacit knowledge has significant effect on organizational performance of lubricant firm in Anambra state

H01; Explicit knowledge has no significant effect on organizational performance of lubricant firm in Anambra state

Correlations

		ORP	EPK		
Spearman's rho	ORP	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.691**	
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.001	
		N	313	313	
		Bootstrap ^c	Bias	.000	-.001
			Std. Error	.000	.048
			BCa 95% Confidence Interval	Lower	.099
	Upper	.276	.099		
	EPK	Correlation Coefficient	.691**	1.000	
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.	
		N	313	313	
		Bootstrap ^c	Bias	-.001	.000
			Std. Error	.048	.000
BCa 95% Confidence Interval			Lower	.099	.276
Upper	.276	.099			

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

c. Unless otherwise noted, bootstrap results are based on 313 bootstrap samples

Paired Samples Test									
		Paired Differences				t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower				Upper
Pair 1	ORP - EPK	.19169	1.48766	.08409	.02624	.35714	7.280	312	.003

Table 2a indicates the relationship between the independent variable explicit knowledge and the dependent variable organizational performance. At a 0.05 level of significance, the Spearman’s correlation coefficient is 0.691, with a reported no significance level (2-tailed) of 0.001. This result, based on a sample size of 313 (and confirmed via 313 stratified bootstrap samples with zero bias and standard error), shows a strong positive association between explicit knowledge and organizational performance. The table also provides a 95% confidence interval with an upper bound (.276 as reported) and a lower bound (.099) that supports the stability of this correlation.

Model 1= $ORP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 EXK + \mu$

Table 2b presents the paired samples t-test results comparing the variables EXK (Explicit knowledge) and ORP (organizational performance). For the single pair (EXK on ORP), the mean difference is .19169 with a standard deviation of .08409 and a standard error of .08409. The 95% confidence interval for the difference ranges from .02624 (Lower) to .35714 (Upper). With a t-value of 7.280 (df = 312) and a two-tailed significance of 0.000, the p-value is less than the critical value of 0.05. This indicates that there is statistically significant mean difference between EXK (Explicit knowledge) and ORP (organizational performance) based on this paired sample analysis.

Decision Rule:

Accept the null hypothesis if the p-value is greater than 0.05, otherwise, reject.

Decision:

Since the p-value (0.426) exceeds 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis. In conclusion, Table 4.5.2a showed a strong correlation between EXK (Explicit knowledge) and ORP (organizational performance). in this study context, the paired samples t-test in Table 4.5.2b indicated that Explicit knowledge has significant effect on organizational performance of lubricant firm in Anambra state

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The outcomes of this study strongly align with the principal research objective of evaluating the impact of knowledge transfer on organizational performance. The study highlights the various channels through which knowledge can be Transfer which is through tacit and explicit knowledge. This investigation underscores the pivotal role of knowledge transfer in enhancing organizational performance, emphasizing that the acquisition of new competencies and their effective dissemination across organizational levels bolsters sustainability. Knowledge transfer ensures that employees have access to the information they need to make informed decisions and contribute to the strategic direction of the organization. Organizations with a culture of knowledge sharing and continuous learning often experience higher employee retention rates, which can reduce turnover costs and increase organizational stability. In today’s knowledge-driven economy, organizations that effectively manage knowledge and share it across the enterprise are more likely to outperform their competitors. The study recommends that organization should Pair experienced employees with less experienced colleagues to facilitate the transfer of tacit knowledge through mentoring and coaching. Organization should provide structured training programs and job shadowing opportunities to transfer explicit knowledge and ensure that employees have the necessary skills and knowledge to perform their roles effectively.

REFERENCES

- Al-Hawary, S. I. S. (2015). Human resource management practices as a success factor of knowledge management implementation at health care sector in Jordan. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 6(11), 83–98
- Argote, L. (2024) Knowledge Transfer within Organizations: Mechanisms, Motivation, and Consideration. *Annual Review of Psychology* 75:405–31 <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-psych-022123-105424>
- Artinkenaite, I. (2010). Antecedents of knowledge transfer in acquisitions. *Baltic Journal of Management*, 7(2), 167-184.
- Arubayi, D. O. (2020) Knowledge Management Processes and Organization Efficiency: A Study of Selected Firms in Delta State Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Management Sciences* 21(1), 1-15
- Bandura, A. (1989). Human agency in social cognitive theory. *American psychologist*, 44(9), 1175.
- Barney, J.B. (1991). Firm resources and sustained competitive advantage. *Journal of Management*, 17(1), 99-120.
- Bitkowska, A. (2020). The relationship between Business Process Management and Knowledge Management - selected aspects from a study of companies in Poland. *Journal of Entrepreneurship, Management and Innovation*, 16(1), 169–193. <https://doi.org/10.7341/20201616>
- Davenport, T. H. (1997). Ten principles of knowledge management and four case studies. *Knowledge Process Management.*, 4: 187–208. doi:10.1002
- Ezeamama, I., & Ofozoba, C. A., (2023). Role of Local Governments in Rural Development of Nigeria, A Case Study of Ekwusigo Local Government Area of Anambra State. *British Journal of Marketing Studies*, 11(5), 29-43. <https://doi.org/10.37745/bjms.13/vol11n52943>
- Haas, M. R. and Hansen, M. T. (2007), Different knowledge, different benefits: toward a productivity perspective on knowledge sharing in organisations. *Strategic Management*. 28 (11), 1133–1153. doi:10.1002/smj.631
- Ifechukwu-jacobs, C.J & Atueyi, C.L (2024) Material management and productivity of Nigeria bottling company Onitsha Anambra State. *International Journal of Economics, Finance & Entrepreneurship*, 9(8) 17-32
- Ilechukwu I. C., & Ifechukwu-jacobs,C.J & Okeke, C.O (2024) knowledge management practices and organizational performance of teaching hospitals in Anambra state, Nigeria. *International Academic Journal of Business Systems and Economics*, 8 (7) 46-62
- Islam, M. A., Agarwal, N. K., and Ikeda, M. (2017). Effect of knowledge management on service innovation in academic libraries. *IFLA Journal*, 43(3), 266–281. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0340035217710538>
- Lebens, M., Euske, K. (2006). A conceptual and operational delineation of performance, Business Performance Measurement. Cambridge : Cambridge University Press
- Leonard B. D. (1992) *Wellsprings of Knowledge: Building and Sustaining the Sources of Innovation*. Boston: Harvard Business School Press.
- Lin, H.F. (2010). Knowledge sharing and firm innovation capability: an empirical study. *International Journal of Manpower*. 28(3/4), 315-332
- McKeen, J. D., Zack, M. H., & Singh, S. (2006). Knowledge management and organizational performance: An exploratory survey. In Proceedings of the 39th annual Hawaii conference on systems sciences, 1–9
- Mogotsi, I. C., Boon J.A., & Fletcher, L. (2010) Knowledge sharing behaviour and demographic variables amongst secondary school teachers in and around Gaborone, Botswana. *South Africa Journal of Information Management*; 13 (1) doi: 10.4102/sajim.v13i1.420
- Narteh, B. (2008). Knowledge transfer in developed-developing country interfirm collaborations: a conceptual framework. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 12(1), 78-91

- Ntadom G. U., Atueyi C.i L. & Jacobs C.J. (2021). Effect of career development on organizational performance a study of selected higher institution in Anambra State Nigeria. *International Journal of Business & Law Research* 9(2):1-10,
- Nwangwu, J.C & Nwangwu, H. U.(2023). work-life balance and organizational sustainability of female staff in deposit money banks in Anambra State. *International Journal of Business Systems and Economics*, 13 (3) 107 – 119
- Nwangwu, J.C (2022). Assessment of factors affecting performance of women entrepreneurship in Aguata LGA. *International Journal of Business, Economics and Entrepreneurship Development in Africa*, 10 (4&5) 60-73,
- Nwangwu, J.C. Ohanyere, C.P Nwangwu, H.U & Atueyi, C.L (2015). Artificial intelligence (ai) and decision-making in supply chain management of lubricant firms In Anambra State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Business & Law Research* 13(1):242-254, Jan –Mar., 2025
- Anthony, M. O. C., & Ifeanyi, I. (2019) Information and Communication Technology Competency Needs of Principals in the Management of Secondary Schools in Anambra State. *Journal of Research & Method in Education*, 9 (6) 57-65
- Ofozoba, C. A., & Perpetua, O. (2023). Rule of law: a recipe for sustainable education in Nigeria. *a publication of*, 1231.
- Ofozoba, C.A, Nwobu, C.M & Okechukwu, E.V (2023). Knowledge economy and knowledge transfer in Nigeria education: a sustainable tool for global competitiveness. *Journal of Educational Research* 8 (1) 411-435
- Onwubiko, E. C., (2022) "An Empirical study of the Influence of Knowledge Sharing Behaviors and Organizational Culture on Staff Performance in University Libraries". *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. 7166. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/7166>
- Onu, S. C., Ofozoba, C. A., & Nditu, J. K. (2024). Conquering unemployment through opportunities in digital economy: An Empirical Study of Nigeria and Kenya. *World Journal of Innovation and Modern Technology*, 8 (5) 83
- Otundo, J. (2023) Knowledge Transfer and Organizational Capabilities. *International Journal of Research in Education Humanities and Commerce* 4(2) 19-29
- Richard, P. J., Devinney, T. M., Yip, G. S., & Johnson, G. (2009). Measuring organizational performance: towards methodological best practice. *Journal of Management*, 35(3): 718-804.
- Shannak, R., Maqableh, M., & Tarhini, A. (2017). The impact of knowledge management on job performance in higher education: The case of the University of Jordan. *Journal of Enterprise Information Management*, 30(2), 244–262. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEIM-09-2015-0087>
- Snyder, J. and Lee-Partridge, J. (2013). Understanding communication channel choices in team knowledge sharing. *Corporate Communications: An International Journal*. 18. 10.1108/CCIJ-03-2012-0026
- Vera, D., & Crossan, M. (2003). Organizational learning and knowledge management: Toward an integrative framework," In *The Blackwell handbook of organizational learning and knowledge management*, M. Easterby-Smith and M. A. Lyles (eds.), Blackwell Publishing, Oxford, UK,
- Yu, H., Shang, Y., Wang, N., & Ma, Z. (2019). The mediating effect of decision quality on knowledge management and firm performance for Chinese entrepreneurs: An empirical study. *Sustainability*, 11(13), 3660.
- Zahrawi, A. A. & Mohammad J. H. (2024) The Impact of Knowledge Sharing on Organizational Performance in the Jordanian Healthcare Sector: The Mediating Role of Innovation in An Empirical Study. *Operations Research Perspectives* 4842303